

Effect of Discipline, Employee Work Conflict, and Work Environment on Increasing Employees Work Quality at PT. Metalindo's Main Techniques during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of discipline (X1), employee work conflict (X2), and work environment (X3) on improving the quality of work of employees (Y) at PT. Metalindo Teknik Utama during the Covid-19 pandemic. This study uses a quantitative descriptive method conducted at PT. Metalindo Teknik Utama, Karawang. Research data obtained through a questionnaire. The subjects of this study were employees at PT. Metalindo Teknik Utama and there are 50 respondents. Sampling using a non-probability sampling technique, namely purposive sampling with the number of respondents as many as 32 people. The results of data analysis show that discipline (X1) and work environment (X3) have a partial and significant effect on improving the quality of employees' work. Meanwhile, employee work conflict (X2) has a partial and insignificant effect on improving the quality of employees' work. The conclusion is discipline, employee work conflict and work environment have a simultaneous effect on improving the quality of employee work.

Keywords: *Discipline, Work Conflict, Work Environment, Employee Quality.*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a major impact on various fields. Covid-19 itself represents the 2019 coronavirus disease. This infectious disease was discovered in the city of Wuhan, China at the end of 2019. Its rapid spread throughout the world made the World Health Organization (WHO), designate this infectious disease as a global pandemic. One of the sectors affected by this pandemic is the economic sector. This impact can affect the development of the company globally. This event encourages companies to find solutions to these problems in order to survive during the Covid-19 pandemic.

One solution that is important and can be taken is the management of the workforce or employees. According to Kiswuryanto (2014: 2), one of the problems of human resources is still in the spotlight and the focus of the company to survive in the era of globalization. Employees have an important role in every activity of the company. Although with support by facilities and infrastructure as well as resources, the company's activities will not be completed properly without the support of reliable human resources. This result shows that human resources are one of the important keys that should be put with high consideration including all their needs. As an essential thing, human resources will determine the success of a company in carrying out its activities. Hence, companies need to use their human resources to be more efficient and efficient, so that company activities can run smoothly (Jamaludin, 2017). Good human resource management will also lead to an increase in the quality and performance of employees.

Discipline is the key to the success of a company in achieving its goals. In accordance with Hasibuan's (2017) statement that discipline is the most important function of Human Resource Management (HR) and the key to achieving goals because without a good discipline, it will be difficult to achieve maximum goals. Another factor that can affect the running of a company is the existence of employee work conflicts. Excessive or too low levels of conflict can be an obstacle to the company's effectiveness in achieving high customer service quality (Royani, 2016). Conflict is motivated by a discrepancy or difference in terms of values, goals, status, and so on. In addition to the factors behind the occurrence of a conflict, symptoms that arise in an organization when a conflict occurs are when an individual or group shows a hostile attitude toward other individuals or groups that affect performance in carrying out organizational activities (Aldionita, 2014: 414). In addition to work discipline and employee work conflicts, the work environment is also a success factor in a company. The work environment also plays an important part in improving employee performance (Rahmawanti, 2014: 2).

There have been previous studies on discipline, employee work conflict, and work environment. One of them is research conducted by Hustia (2020). The variables studied for their influence on employee performance are work motivation, work environment, and work discipline. The results of his research indicate that the third variable has an effect on

employee performance, either partially or jointly. Another study was conducted by Herdani, Suwarsi, and Harahap (2021). This study examines the effect of work motivation and work conflict on employee performance. The results showed that work motivation had a positive effect on employee performance. Work conflict also has a significant positive effect on employee performance. It is also concluded that the second variable has an effect on employee performance at the same time.

Phenomena related to discipline, employee work conflicts, and the perceived work environment in a company, PT. Metalindo Teknik Utama, Tangerang. Indicates that the employee has a disciplinary problem. Especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, the intensity of work conflicts among employees is increasing. Both of these things can lead to the creation of an unhealthy work environment and can affect the quality of work of employees.

Based on this background, this research aims to determine the impact of discipline, employee work conflict, and work environment on improving the quality of PT employees' work. Metalindo Teknik Utama during the Covid-19 pandemic. Hence, we conducted a study entitled "Impact of Work Discipline (X1), Employee Work Conflict (X2), and Work Environment (X3) as Factors That Can Improve Work Quality Improvement (Y) of PT Employees." Metalindo Teknik Utama during the Covid-19 pandemic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Discipline

According to Hasibuan (2017), work discipline is a person's awareness in obeying all applicable social rules and norms. Meanwhile, Sastrohardiwiryo (2003) revealed that work discipline is an attitude or behavior that respects, appreciates and obeys the rules and norms, both written and unwritten, and services, so that they will not give action and resistance when given sanctions, when violating.

Based on this opinion, discipline is a person's attitude that is carried out consciously to respect and obey all applicable written and unwritten rules. The indicators of discipline according to Hasibuan (2017) are: 1) attendance at work; 2) level of alertness; 3) fulfillment of work standards; 4) compliance with work regulations; and 5) work ethic.

Employee Work Conflict

According to Mangkunegara (2017), conflict is something that occurs between what a person expects from himself, other people, organizations, and the reality he expects. Putri, Nuryanti, and Rifki (2017) conflict in the work context is a type of interaction in the form or antagonist that occurs between two or more people in a company. Therefore, the nature of conflict refers to everything in the form of interactions that occur between two or more people in a company that is expected to occur.

According to Muchlas (2008) there are two factors that can be considered as causes or sources of conflict, namely: 1) Communication, in communicating, 2) Structure, where the larger the structure, the greater the possibility of conflict. Work conflict is divided into two, namely functional conflict and dysfunctional conflict. Functional conflict is a conflict that is useful to achieve company goals. While dysfunctional conflict is a conflict that will hinder the achievement of company goals. Experiencing conflict can lead to failure, confrontation, and disruption to employees' work (Massey & Dawes, 2004).

Work environment

According to Sedarmayanti (2017), the work environment is the entire building in the form of tools and materials, work environment, work methods, and work arrangements in which a person works, both individually and in groups. The work environment is one of the most important things in getting the job done. The work environment is the atmosphere around the location where a person works, which can be in the form of rooms, facilities, or working relationships with colleagues (Paramita, 2018). Hence, the work environment is an atmosphere that can be in the form of facilities, work environment, methods, and working relationships between individuals and co-workers, both individuals and groups. The company's work environment can show that employees will produce good work results if they are in accordance with the company and how it works. Fitriana (2013: 192) suggests that the indicators of the work environment include communication errors, differences in goals, differences in perceptions, interdependence of work activities, and errors in affection. Meanwhile, according to Sedarmayanti (2009), the factors that affect the work environment are lighting, temperature, noise, color, and layout/space, safety and employee relations. In this study, indicators used include communication errors, differences in goals, affection errors, work atmosphere (facilities), and employee relations.

Employee Work Quality

Humanization requires continuous human resource development in order to obtain quality human resources and make the work carried out produce the expected results. What is meant by quality is being able to meet the qualifications

required in the work, so that it can be completed as planned. Work quality is a person's behavior in the company concept which is classified as a company condition formed through management's efforts to improve the welfare of employees' lives (Setiyadi, Wartini, and Wijayanto, 2016). Employee performance can be observed from three aspects, namely the quality of work, quantity of work, and position. According to Matutina (2011), indicators of employee work quality include knowledge, skills, and abilities. Knowledge is the ability of employees to produce intelligence and thinking skills. Skills, namely the level of mastery of operating technology staff in a particular field. The capabilities in question are several competencies, which include loyalty, cooperation, and responsibility.

Hypothesis

Ho: Discipline, employee work conflict and work environment have no effect on improving the quality of employee work.
 H1: Discipline, employee work conflicts and working environment have an impact on improving the quality of employees' work.

METHOD

The analytical method used is descriptive analysis, inferential analysis and multiple linear regression analysis. This research was conducted at PT. Metalindo Teknik Utama or commonly known as MTU Karoseri is located in Jl. East Karawang, Toll Gate, Ds. Anggadita, Kec. Klari, Kab. Karawang-West, Java. The population in this study was employees of PT. Metalindo Teknik Utama, has a total of 50 employees. The sampling method used in this study is a non-probability sampling technique, namely purposive sampling. The author stipulates that the sampling standard is the employees of PT. Metalindo Teknik, Utama, who has worked for at least 1 year, is willing to be a research interviewee. The number of samples in this study were 32 employees. This study uses primary and secondary data. Almost all data were obtained through a questionnaire with a Likert scale. While secondary data is the result of documentation which can be in the form of documents. The data obtained were then processed by descriptive statistical analysis, classical assumption test, and hypothesis testing. Statistical analysis consists of validity and reliability tests. Classical assumption test includes normality test, heteroscedasticity test, and multicollinearity test. While the hypothesis test is multiple linear regression analysis, T test, F test, and the coefficient of determination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Respondents

The data collection method was completed by distributing questionnaires to 32 employees of PT. Metalindo's main technology. Table 1. The following are the characteristics of the interviewees.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Total	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	21	65.6
Female	11	34.4
Age		
<20 years	0	0
20-25 years	19	59.4
26-30 years	7	21.9
31-35 years	5	15.6
>35 years	1	3.1

Table 1 shows that the number of male respondents was 21 people, while the female respondents were 11 people. In other words, the ratio of male to female respondents was 2:1. In terms of age characteristics, there are 32 respondents, of which 1 respondent's age is 20-25 years old and 7 respondents are between 26-30 years old.

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity tests are used to measure the effectiveness of measurement tools used in research. The questionnaire is appropriate to use if the question or statement can reveal a phenomenon that is felt or experienced by the respondents included in the research sample. In this study, the researchers used a validity test to ensure the level of relevance of the questionnaire as a research measurement tool, regardless of whether it is feasible or not as the data to be tested in the research. Tests were carried out on each independent variable and dependent variable.

The results of the validity test in this study, almost all the tools used proved efficacious because they had a Sig<alpha value. However, the X3.4 instrument on the Work Environment variable is declared invalid because it has a significance value of 0.306, which is known to be $0.360 > 0.05$.

Based on the data processing that has been done, it is known that the Cronbach alpha obtained for each variable shows that each variable is declared reliable since it has a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.794 Discipline (X1), 0.889 Corporate Conflict (X2), 0.766 Work Environment (X3), and 0.924 Employee Work Quality (Y) in the High category, according to the statement put forward by Sugiyono (2016).

Classic assumption test

This test is used to determine whether the number of samples taken is representative or not, so that conclusions drawn from a number of samples can be clarified.

Table 2. Normality Test Results
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		32
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.63670524
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.193
	Positive	.193
	Negative	-.077
Test Statistic		.193
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.004 ^c
Exact Sig. (2-tailed)		.160
Point Probability		.000

- a. Normal, test distribution.
- b. Calculated from the datum.
- c. Significance of Lilliefors.

Based on the Kolmogorov Smirnov normality test, the Exact Sig result is 0.160. This result means that the data used in this study is normally distributed because $0.160 > 0.005$.

Based on the heteroscedasticity test that has been carried out, the results obtained are that:

Figure 1. Heteroscedasticity

Test Results as we can see from the picture above, the variables in this study have no symptoms of heteroscedasticity. Based on the multicollinearity test that has been carried out, the following results were obtained:

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Results
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	3.413	5.659		.603	.551		
	X1	.359	.140	.351	2.568	.016	.569	1.756
	X2	.279	.150	.291	1.863	.073	.436	2.293
	X3	.407	.173	.332	2.356	.026	.538	1.858

a. Dependent Variable: Y

It can be seen from the table above that the tolerance value obtained for each independent variable is greater than 0.10. Thus, it can be said that there are no signs of multicollinearity in the variables studied.

Hypothesis test

Table 4. t Test Results
Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.413	5.659		.603	.551
	X1	.359	.140	.351	2.568	.016
	X2	.279	.150	.291	1.863	.073
	X3	.407	.173	.332	2.356	.026

a. Dependent Variable: Y

It can be said that each variable has a t-count value, and its significance is different from the t-test that has been done above. The calculated t value obtained for the variable (X1) is 2.568, which indicates that this value is greater than the 1.6938 used in the t table. A significance value of 0.016 also indicates that it is less than 0.05. This event concludes that the discipline variable has a partial and significant positive effect on improving the quality of employees' work.

The test results for employee work conflicts (X2) stated that the t-count value was 1.863 with a significance value of 0.073. The conclusion is that the t-count value is greater than the t-table value ($t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$), and the obtained significance value indicates that the result is > 0.05 . Based on these two findings, it is concluded that the variable of employee work conflict has a partial and insignificant positive effect on improving the quality of employees' work.

The calculated value in the working environment variable (X3) is 2.356, so it is greater than the table value ($\text{count} > \text{table}$). In addition, the significance value is not greater than 0.05, that is, 0.026. Based on these two things, the conclusion obtained is that the work environment variable has a partial and significant positive effect on improving the quality of employees' work.

Table 5. F Test Results

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	506.481	3	168.827	21.934	.000^b
	Residual	215.519	28	7.697		
	Total	722.000	31			

- a. Dependent Variable: Y
- b. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

Table 5 shows that the linear regression model carried out has an Fcount value of 21,934. This value suggests a value greater than the table value used, which is 2.95. HenceTherefore, it can be concluded that Fcount>Ftable. When viewed from the level of significance, the value obtained is 0.00, where the value is smaller than 0.05. Based on these two considerations, it was found that the variables of discipline, employee work conflict, and work environment together had an effect on improving the quality of employees' work. This result also means that the hypothesis H1 is accepted. Multiple Regression Analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis is used to analyze the data also to determine the effect of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). The general equation for multiple regression analysis in this study is: $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3$.

Information:

Y: Variable of improving employee's work quality

a: Constant

b1, b2, b3: Regression coefficient

X1: Discipline variable

X2: Employee work, conflict variable

X3: Work environment, variable

Table 6. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.413	5.659		.603	.551
	X1	.359	.140	.351	2.568	.016
	X2	.279	.150	.291	1.863	.073
	X3	.407	.173	.332	2.356	.026

- a. Dependent Variable: Y

In Table 6, the obtained linear regression equations are: $Y = 3.413 + 0.359X_1 + 0.279X_2 + 0.407X_3$. This equation explains several things, as follows: First, the termination coefficient value is 3.413, meaning that if the variables of discipline, employee work conflict, and work environment are considered zero, then the increase in the quality of employee work remains positive for the coefficient value. Second, the discipline variable (X1) shows a positive value of 0.359. That is, if the discipline variable increases, the quality of the employee's work also increases. Furthermore, for the employee work conflict variable (X2) the value is also positive, namely 0.279. These results mean that employee work conflict is directly proportional to the increase in the quality of employee work. If employee work conflict increases, the quality of employee work will also increase. Finally, the value for the work environment variable (X3) is 0.407. These results show that if the work environment variable increases, the quality of work of employees will also increase.

Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination (R²), aims to find out how much is the independent variable's ability to explain the dependent variable we can display in SPSS. Based on the tests that have been carried out, the results of the coefficient of determination are obtained as follows:

Table 7. Results of the Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.838 ^a	.701	.670	2.774

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2

The above table shows that the R-squared value is 0.701. In other words, the independent variables in this study can explain 70.1% of the dependent variables, and 29.9% are affected by other variables. This figure is quite large in terms of showing the strength of the influence of these variables.

CONCLUSION

Results of the obtained data analysis show the conclusions of this study which include: 1. Discipline has a huge effect on improving the work quality of PT. Metalindo's main technique, during the covid-19 pandemic. 2. Employee work conflict has no significant effect on improving the quality of work of employees, PT. Metalindo's main technique, during the covid-19 pandemic. 3. The work environment has a very large influence on improving the quality of work of PT. Metalindo's main technique, during the covid-19 pandemic. 4. Discipline, employee work conflict and work environment have a simultaneous effect on improving the quality of work at PT. Metalindo's main technique, during the covid-19 pandemic.

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